

CLINICOPATHOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION WITH MOLECULAR SUBTYPES OF BREAST CANCER

Yashaswini Puranam¹, Sameera Reddy Mula¹, Sucharitha Sadula¹, Vyshnavi Racharla¹.

Varshini Erroju², Ezhilarasi Ravindran³

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Vaageswari College of Pharmacy¹

Assistant professor, Vaageswari college of Pharmacy²

Department of Oncology, CAIMS- Cancer Research Institute.

Corresponding author: Yashaswini Puranam

Received: Apr 04, 2026

Accepted: Apr 25, 2026

Published: Apr 29, 2026

ABSTRACT

Background:

Breast cancer is a complex condition with a variety of characteristics and therapeutic approaches. Based on the status of the receptors as assessed by immunohistochemistry, it can be divided into: Luminal A, Luminal B, HER2-enriched, and TNBC.

Evaluating the relationship between clinicopathological characteristics and molecular subtypes, when combined with descriptive analysis of treatment strategies, provides significant insights into disease patterns and therapeutic practices.

Methodology:

The study included 300 histopathologically confirmed breast cancer patients with immunohistochemistry data for receptor status. Statistical analysis was done to evaluate the association between clinicopathological parameters and molecular subtypes.

Result:

Postmenopausal women were in a greater proportion (80%), with lump as the most prevalent symptom (76.6%). The commonest molecular subtype was TNBC. Luminal A and TNBC were mostly seen in older women in the study, whereas in younger women, TNBC was more common. Luminal cancers were treated with hormone therapy, for HER2-enriched tumours, targeted therapy was used and chemotherapy for TNBC.

Conclusion:

There was a statistical significance found between the subtypes and clinical and pathological parameters of breast cancer. Descriptive analysis of treatment decisions demonstrates current clinical practice and reveals how patient and disease-related factors and molecular subtypes influence the therapeutic approach.

Keywords: *Molecular subtypes, Immunohistochemistry, Clinicopathological parameters. Management approach.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is a heterogeneous malignancy that arises from the mammary tissue, where the cancerous cells divide more frequently and rapidly than normal healthy ones ^[1]. This refers to the growth and proliferation of virulent cells within the tissue. The breast is composed of two types of tissue: glandular and stromal. The glandular tissue includes milk-producing glands and ducts, whereas the stromal tissue contains the fatty and fibrous connective tissue. ^[2]

Figure 1. Anatomy

EPIDEMIOLOGY:

The information taken from GLOBOCAN 2022 states that breast carcinoma is the predominant cancer in the world. India ranks third globally and leads in mortality with 98,337 deaths in 2022. Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) due to this have increased.

CLASSIFICATION:

HISTOLOGICAL:

a) Invasive Breast Carcinoma: The neoplastic cells invade the surrounding fatty and fibrous tissue. It is of two types, i.e.,

(IDC): The carcinomatous cells begin in the milk ducts and then infiltrate

(ILC) The cancerous cells start in the milk glands and then invade.

b) Non-invasive Breast Carcinoma: The cells do not invade and are often confined to the ducts or lobules.

Ductal Carcinoma In-situ (DCIS): There is an increase in the cells within the ducts

Lobular Carcinoma In-situ (LCIS): Hyperproliferation of the cells inside the lobules^[2].

MOLECULAR:

Based on immunohistochemical expression of receptors- ER/PR, HER2,

Luminal A:

Immunohistochemistry expression: Positive hormone receptors.

Ki-67 index: Low (<20%)

Characteristics: Low-grade, slow-growing.

Treatment: Shows a good response to hormone therapy

Luminal B:

Immunohistochemistry expression: Estrogen receptors are present

Ki-67 index: Greater (>20%)

Characteristics: High-grade, fast-growing

Treatment: Respond to hormone therapy and chemotherapy

HER2 type:

Immunohistochemistry expression: Presence of Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor

These are subcategorised into two:

- HER2 Enriched- ER/PR negative, HER2 positive, Ki67 >20%.
- Luminal HER2 (Triple positive)- ER/PR +, HER2 +, Ki67 <20%.

Treatment: Targeted therapy (Trastuzumab, Pertuzumab)

Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC):

Immunohistochemistry expression: Negative for all 3 receptors

Characteristics: Associated with alterations in the DNA repair genes, higher proliferation and increased genomic instability.

RISK FACTORS:

Non- modifiable	Modifiable
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female sex (due to enhanced hormonal stimulation). It can also occur in males, but it is very rare (<1%). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity • Body mass index (BMI) • Alcohol intake

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Older age • Family history • Genetic mutations (genes involved: BRCA1, BRCA2) • Reproductive Hx (exposure to estro and progesterone, pregnancy, breastfeeding, menarche, and menopause) • Density of stroma. • PMHx of mammary pathology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processed foods • Exposure to chemicals.
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TREATMENT:**SURGERY:****MASTECTOMY:**

It involves removing all or a portion of the breast gland, frequently along with the nipple-areola complex. It comes in four varieties: Radical, Modified radical, Simple and Partial. The most appropriate method of treatment is chosen based on the patient's choices, the tumour size and its location. Out of 30 and 45%, about 13% of them undergo a contralateral prophylactic mastectomy.

- a) **Modified Radical Mastectomy (MRM)**
- b) **Breast Conserving Surgery (BCS)**
- c) **Contralateral Prophylactic Mastectomy (CPM)**

RADIATION THERAPY:

This uses high-energy radiation to kill cancer cells.

The following are forms of radiation treatment:

- i. **EBRT (External Beam Radiation Therapy):**
 - a) **Radiation to the whole breast:**
 - b) **Partially accelerated breast radiation:**
- ii. **BRACHYTHERAPY:**

It is called as internal radiation; a radioactive pellet containing device is inserted into the breast tissue in the tumour bed for a brief period.

Various types of brachytherapy:

- Intracavitary brachytherapy
- Interstitial brachytherapy

CHEMOTHERAPY:

It is best to choose the right course of treatment based on the condition of each patient to prevent both over- and under-treatment.

Chemo can be of two types: **Neo-adjuvant chemotherapy, Adjuvant chemotherapy**

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Setting	Chalmeda Ananda Rao Institute of Medical Sciences- Cancer Hospital and Research Institute, Karimnagar (CAIMS- Cancer Hospital and Research Institute)
Study Setting	Chalmeda Ananda Rao Institute of Medical Sciences- Cancer Hospital and Research Institute, Karimnagar (CAIMS- Cancer Hospital and Research Institute)
Evaluation approach	Cross-sectional observational study
Duration	6 months
No. of Participants	300 Breast Cancer Patients
Included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female BC patients of >18 years • Histopathologically confirmed disease
Excluded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male breast cancer patients • Patients <18 years

Data collection process:

Medical records were reviewed systematically for clinical and pathological characteristics of cancer.

- Data was collected using a pre-formatted data collection form.
- Treatment approaches from the case files were documented, maintaining patient confidentiality.

Statistical Analysis:

- Descriptive statistics: frequency, percentage.
- Chi-square test to assess associations.
- P-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 31 was used.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study shows a clear association between clinicopathological characteristics and molecular subtypes of breast cancer and their respective treatment modalities

A total of 300 female breast cancer patients were included in this study

Interpretation:

Out of 300 patients, most were aged >56 years (45.33%) and 44–56 years (38.66%). The majority were literate (59.3%) and from rural areas (72%). Most had normal BMI (52%), while the rest were nearly equally underweight (24.6%) and overweight (23.3%).

PARAMETER	MOLECULAR SUBTYPES				x ²	df	p-value
	Luminal A (n=84)	Luminal B (n=70)	HER2- enriched (n=56)	TNBC (n=90)			
Age					18.278	9	0.032
18-30 (n=4)	4	0	0	0			
31-43 (n=44)	10	10	10	14			
44-56 (n=116)	26	30	28	32			
>56 (n=136)	44	30	18	44			
Body mass index					18.334	6	0.005
18-25 (n=156)	46	36	36	38			
<18 (n=74)	12	16	12	34			
>25 (n=70)	26	18	8	18			
Menstrual status					8.911	6	0.179
Pre-menopausal (n=30)	8	2	8	12			
Peri-menopausal (n=30)	6	6	6	12			
Post-menopausal (n=240)	70	62	42	66			
Parity					17.005	9	0.049
0 (n=24)	6	6	8	4			
1 (n=84)	20	26	10	28			
2 (n=120)	30	28	22	40			
>3 (n=72)	28	10	16	18			

Presenting complaints					20.108	6	0.003
Breast lump (n=230)	62	58	44	66			
Breast lump + other symptoms (n=40)	14	10	10	6			
Non-lump symptoms (n=30)	8	2	2	18			
Duration of complaints					14.103	6	0.029
<3 months (n=174)	42	40	34	58			
3-6 months(n=52)	14	16	4	18			
>6 months (n=74)	28	14	18	14			
Tumor size					28.759	6	<0.001
<2cm (n=84)	18	26	18	22			
2-5cm (n=176)	64	38	24	50			
>5cm (n=40)	2	6	14	18			
Staging					13.000	9	0.163
I (n=10)	4	2	4	0			
II (n=168)	50	44	22	54			
III (n=102)	24	22	26	30			
IV (n=20)	6	4	4	6			
Histological grade					13.024	6	0.043
I (n=22)	10	6	4	2			
II (n=220)	64	54	38	64			
III (n=58)	10	10	14	24			

Interpretation:

Significant associations were observed between molecular sub types and age, BMI, parity, presenting complaints, duration of complaints, tumor size and histological grade, whereas menstrual status and tumor stage showed no significant association. The aggressive subtypes like TNBC, HER 2 enriched were grouped in younger, low BMI patients with larger, high-grade tumours, whereas luminal A, luminal B predominate in older patients with smaller, well-differentiated tumours.

IV CONCLUSION:

A substantial association was found between molecular subtypes and clinicopathological parameters, emphasising the disease's biological variability and the necessity for personalised treatment methods. The observed treatment patterns are consistent with standard clinical practice, indicating that therapeutic decisions are influenced by molecular subtypes as well as patient and illness characteristics.

Raising breast cancer awareness, encouraging early symptom recognition and screening, and providing timely access to diagnostic and molecular testing are critical steps toward improving early detection, optimising treatment selection, and lowering breast cancer-related morbidity and mortality.

V Acknowledgement

The author acknowledges the support of Vaageswari College of Pharmacy and all participants who contributed to this study

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